

INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING AS A MEANS OF INFORMATION TRANSMISSION TOWARDS CONSUMER: THEORETICAL ASPECT

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Abstract. The article analyses the term of “advertising” with the focus on information transmission function and a possibility to influence consumers. A comparative analysis of advertising terms is completed. The article presents a different view towards areas of advertising functions and presents aspects of advertising influence on consumers. These aspects form a formula of CAFE³A – cognition, action, finances, emotions and advantage (Lith. PEFEN). There cognition is understood as feelings and recollections of a consumer. Action means that a consumer has noticed and read the ad. Financial aspect of the formula is connected to the costs consumer experiences. Emotional component of advertising impact includes evaluations how consumers accept and value the chosen product. Finally, advantage means the relations among such factors as financial costs, emotions for the bought product and experienced use of a product.

Keywords: advertising, advertising function areas, advertising influence on consumers.

REKLAMOS, KAIP INFORMACIJOS PERDAVIMO PRIEMONĖS, ĮTAKA VARTOTOJUI: TEORINIS ASPEKTAS

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Santrauka. Straipsnyje analizuojama reklamos sąvoka, akcentuojama informacijos perdavimo funkcija, galimybė daryti įtaką vartotojams. Atlikta reklamos sąvokų lyginamoji analizė. Straipsnyje pateikiamas skirtingas požiūris į reklamos funkcijų sritis, išdėstomi reklamos poveikio vartotojui aspektai, atitinkantys PEFEN formulę vertinant reklamos poveikį vartotojui (angl. CAFE³A). Čia pažinimas yra susijęs su vartotojo pojūčiais ir prisiminimais. Elgesio požiūriu – kai žmogus pastebėjo ir perskaitė reklamą, jos poveikis gali būti dar jaučiamas. Finansinis aspektas susijęs su vartotojo išlaidomis, kurioms reklama gali turėti įtakos. Emocinis reklamos poveikio komponentas nustatomas emociniais santykiais su reklamuojamu objektu, t. y. kaip žmogus vertina reklamuojamą prekę. Naudos poveikis apima vartotojo patirtų finansinių išlaidų, emocijų išgytą daiktui ir patirtos naudos santykius.

Reikšminiai žodžiai: reklama, reklamos funkcijos, reklamos įtaka vartotojui.

1. Introduction

An expanding stream of advertising, upspringing new advertising carriers call researchers' attention to the problems of social, psychological, economical effectiveness of advertising, its role in cultural and social life of a country and a city. Advertising businessmen, introducing a new means of advertising into the market, emphasize its advantages, the possibilities to reach the audience. (Vveinhardt, Tamutienė, 2005).

The scientific problem is the inadequate interpretation of the concept of advertising, its functions and influence on consumers.

The object of the article is the influence of advertising on consumers.

The aim of the article is to define the concept of *advertising*, discussing the influence of advertising on consumers.

The goals of the research are:

- To explore different attitudes towards the concept of advertising,
- To introduce the key functions of advertising,
- To define the influence of advertising, as a means of transfer of information, on consumers.

The methods of the research are comparative analysis of scientific literature, systematising and generalisation.

2. The concept of advertising as a means of transfer of information

Build a better mousetrap, the saying goes, and the world will beat a pathway to your door. However, J. Bardeen, a Denver small-business owner, said, that you first have to convince the world that it has mice. (Vijeikis, 2003). An-

other saying – “One half of my advertising budget is wasted. The trouble is, I don't know which half.” – is still suitable today (Kotler, 2004).

In the Lithuanian language we use the term *reklama*, as in the French language *reclame*, derived from a Latin word *reclamo* – shout. In the English language the word *advert* (*advertising*, *advertise*) is used with the meaning „to attract attention to oneself”. This meaning is also related with a Latin word *advertere* – to direct, to concentrate (one's attention, efforts). In the German language the term *Werbung* – agitation, recruitment is used (Čereška, 2004).

According to Behrens (IFAM, 1998), *advertising* is a planned and voluntary form of influence, which has to encourage people to implement the aims of advertising. The Americans call advertising “the second educational system”, as it presents household, social, artistic, scientific and other information about the world in the form, that is clearly understood by the public (Bakanauskas, 2004).

Well-known theorists of advertising define advertising as communication. The aim of such communication is not only to convey information to an addressee, but also to influence a potential consumer, to encourage him to purchase a certain commodity or service. As A. Rogers (1999) states, advertising propagates not only goods, it creates particular images, values, aims, understanding, forms consumers' opinions, and the consumer behaviour depends on them (at Blažinskaitė, 2004).

The conception of advertising is interpreted differently by different authors; therefore a comparative analysis of the concepts of advertising is presented in Table 1.

In all 47 sources of literature and other sources definitions of advertising are presented. Most of them

Table 1. The conception of advertising

No	SOURCES OF LITERATURE	THE CONCEPTION OF ADVERTISING
1.	Adomaitytė, S. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is the art to sell, the synthesis of different sciences (economics, psychology, aesthetics, management, etc.). It is an integral part of contemporary society's conveyance, culture and even art.
2.	Ališauskaitė-Paulavičiūtė, J. (2005)	<i>Advertising</i> is one of the main means, which determine a successful selling of a product or a service.
3.	Bakanauskas, A. (2004)	Firstly, <i>advertising</i> is a means of persuasion, offering, conveyance, a certain means of propaganda. Secondly, goods and services are not advertised for free, advertising is always paid. The advertiser pays for advertising, and a reader or a viewer can understand, who the interested party is. Thirdly, most types of advertising are impersonal. The customer of advertising wants to reach not a particular individual, but a certain target audience, to which advertising is intended.
4.	Barđauskienė, V.; Janulevičiūtė, B. (1999)	<i>Advertising</i> is short, emotionally coloured information, pointed at potential buyers, in order to stimulate different actions, connected with the purchase of goods and services.
5.	Briggs, S. (2001)	<i>Advertising</i> is one of the forms of promotion, able to benefit as a media and a method. Advertising helps create and form the understanding, but not necessarily influence the amount of sales.
6.	Burnett; Moriarty (1997) (at Bakanauskas, 2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is defined as the communication through mass media, paid by a particular identified advertiser, in order to convince or influence target audience.
7.	Čereška, B. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is firstly information about goods, services, their features and forms of realisation, about firms, which produce or sell those goods or services.
8.	Čereška, B. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is a form of communication.
9.	Čereška, B. (2004b)	<i>Advertising</i> is a well-marked phenomenon of contemporary civilisation. It is penetrating and omnipresent.

Table 1 continued

No	SOURCES OF LITERATURE	THE CONCEPTION OF ADVERTISING
10.	Čereška, B. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is impersonal, paid, having the elements of persuasion, disseminated by different means information of a known advertiser about goods, services and ideas on purpose to sell them.
11.	Dubinas, V. (2001)	<i>Advertising</i> is any impersonal presentation of goods, services or ideas, paid by a promoter.
12.	Dubinas, V.; Obelenytė, O. (1993)	<i>Advertising</i> is nothing short of impersonal propagation of goods, services and ideas, paid by the advertiser.
13.	Džonson, S. (1970) (at Āāōōā, 2001)	The branch of <i>advertising</i> is so close to perfection, that it is difficult to propose something to improve it.
14.	Engel (1991); Bowen (1998) (at Bakanauskas, 2004)	The concept of <i>advertising</i> is defined as presentation and propagation of goods, services and ideas, paid by the advertiser.
15.	Hajamas, A. (1999)	<i>Advertising</i> , whatever (graphic, visual or sound) or whenever (indoor, outdoor) it is, is the main sphere of the implementation of creativity.
16.	Janeliauskas, E. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is an integral part of marketing, informing consumers about goods or services on purpose to attract new clients and fighting with market competitors.
17.	Johnson, Dr. (at Kotler, 2003)	The <i>essence of advertising</i> is a promise, a big promise.
18.	Jokubauskas, D. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> may be defined as emotionally coloured information, pointed at potential buyers, in order to stimulate different actions, connected with the purchase of goods and services.
19.	Jokubauskas, D. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is a type of visual art. <i>Advertising</i> is a type of social activity, comprising preparation, production, distribution of different means of advertising, as well as organisation of advertising activity. Advertising is a controlled impact on the audience by the media. <i>Advertising</i> is the ways of forming particular groups of people. <i>Advertising</i> is the art to foist the only motive for consumption, most suitable for most people.
20.	Kotler, P.; Armstrong, G., Saunders, J.; Wong, V. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is impersonal dissemination of information about ideas, products or services, paid by an advertiser in any form.
21.	Kriaučionienė, M.; Urbanskienė, R.; Vaitkienė, R. (2005)	<i>Advertising</i> in the most general sense is non-personal popularization of goods, services and ideas paid by the advertiser.
22.	Leader, Kyritis (1989) (at Bakanauskas, 2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is the art to prepare a correct message and deliver it to target audience correctly.
23.	Martinkus, B.; Neverauskas, B.; Sakalas, A.; Venskus, R.; Žilinskas, V. (2000)	<i>Advertising</i> is the means, which stimulates the demand for a product and sets the favour of a certain type to one or another manufacturer. Advertising is one of the main forms of competition in distinguishing a product. It is used in order to familiarize future buyers with exclusive features of a product and to persuade them that this type of the product is superior than the one offered by competitors.
24.	Maru File, K.; Šliburytė, L. (2001)	<i>Advertising</i> is not a mere transfer of information; it can surprise, shock or even "tame" the market. For this purpose different professional knowledge, specific skills are necessary.
25.	Mažeikaitė, R. (2001 a)	<i>Advertising</i> is one of the forms of marketing communication. Different messages of marketing communication, aimed at improvement of mutual understanding between buyers and sellers in the market, are delivered through it. <i>Advertising</i> not only informs buyers about goods, but also creates their images, which in buyer's opinion become an integral part of particular knowledge on the qualities of advertised goods.
26.	Miliūnaitė, R. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is a strange phenomenon; able to influence us by view, sound, word, it can presume more than something else. It can surprise you pleasantly, sometimes it makes you smile, and sometimes it annoys you and even provokes you. Probably, there are very few people, who are indifferent to it.
27.	Ogilvy, D. (at Jokubauskas, 2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is the liveliest element of business.
28.	Pajuodis, A. (2002)	<i>Advertising</i> is impersonal dissemination of information about goods, services or ideas to the chosen audience, paid by an advertiser on the purpose to reach the objectives set by the advertiser. Advertising disseminates the information, wanted by companies, through certain means of its transfer.
29.	Pajuodis, A. (2005)	<i>Advertising</i> is firstly paid and secondly, it is impersonal, i.e. it is an indirect way of information transfer, and thirdly, there always is its initiator – the advertiser, who usually pays the costs of advertising.
30.	Pass, C.; Lowes, B.; Davies, L. (1997)	<i>Advertising</i> is a means, which stimulates the demand for a product and determines the attachment to a certain type of goods (favour to one or another manufacturer). Advertising is one of the main forms of competition in distinguishing a product. It is used in order to familiarize future buyers with exclusive features of a product and to persuade them that this type of the product is superior than the one offered by competitors
31.	Pickton, Broderick (2001) (at Bakanauskas, 2004)	Part of theorists, defining the concept of <i>advertising</i> , perceives it as mass media.

Table 1 continued

No	SOURCES OF LITERATURE	THE CONCEPTION OF ADVERTISING
32.	Piesarskas, E. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> today is a very powerful instrument of marketing, which affects not only consumers' consciousness, but also their subconsciousness. It influences even such spheres of life as marriage or keeping national rituals of holidays.
33.	Pranulis, V.; Pajuodis, A.; Urbonavičius, S.; Virvilaitė, R. (2000)	<i>Advertising</i> is the means of persuading, offering, i.e. certain propaganda. Advertising is impersonal dissemination of information about goods, services or ideas to the chosen audience, paid by an advertiser on purpose to reach the objectives set by the advertise
34.	Šimašius, R. (2004)	<i>Advertisers</i> declare that advertising is the right to choose. „ <i>Advertising</i> is informational garbage and pollution of brains,“ may a tired of plenty of information recipient of information contradict.
35.	Tarptautinių žodžių žodynas (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is dissemination of news and data about something on purpose to popularize, fame something, to raise the demand.
36.	Urbanskiėnė, R.; Obelenytė, O. (1995)	<i>Advertising</i> is non-personal selling of information presenting and promoting goods, services or ideas, paid by the advertiser.
37.	Urbonavičius, A. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> is like life, very motley.
38.	Vijeikis, J. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is a form of promotion, concerned with mass communication, e.g. commercials and clips in mass media, the advantage of which is a low cost to reach one person. <i>Advertising</i> is useful on purpose to familiarize a buyer with a new commodity and to stimulate his interest or wish to buy that commodity.
39.	Рассел, Дж. Т.; Лейн, У. Р. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is often communication with a potential buyer paid by a known promoter, who places an advertisement in one or several mass media. The character of advertising communication can be measured as persuading. <i>Advertising</i> is not neutral or impersonal; it says, „I want to sell you a commodity or idea“.
40.	Ромат, Е. В. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is a dynamic, quickly transforming sphere of human activity. <i>Advertising</i> is presentation of any paid impersonal proposals and ideas, goods and services on behalf of a known promoter; a form of communication, which tries to adjust the quality of goods and services to the requirements of consumers.
41.	Росситер, Р. Дж., Перси, Л. (2002)	<i>Advertising</i> is the diversion of thoughts or mind so that a consumer would buy a commodity.
42.	Сивулка, Дж. (2002)	<i>Advertising</i> helps people find out about newly emerging goods, and forms the behaviour and wants (the momentum of consumer economy) through this cognitive process.
43.	Фарби, Э. Д. (2004)	<i>Advertising</i> can be defined as a way of dissemination of information. Its function is that every message or proposal has to reach every potential consumer, thereby reaching the set objectives.
44.	Шувалов, В. И. (2003)	<i>Advertising</i> is generally understood as purposeful, paid information about goods or services, also as having a hidden objective – to familiarize a consumer with an advertised commodity and perceive that it is necessary to purchase it.
45.	RECO reklamos studija Kiti šaltiniai [6]	<i>Advertising</i> is an ingenious, voluntary form of impact on people, the purpose of which is certain actions of the people, for example to buy certain goods, support some political parties, public organisations, etc.
46.	Kiti šaltiniai [2]	<i>Advertising</i> is presentation of any form regarding trade, business, craft or profession on purpose to promote provision of goods or services, including realty, rights and duties.
47.	Keršienė, V. Kiti šaltiniai [4]	<i>Advertising</i> is the place, where interests of business and creative work, the needs of consumers and state legal regulation meet. <i>Advertising</i> is a combination of specific competences and professions, which integrate a lot of conceptions, including those oriented towards science and exact data, strategies or problem solving on one hand and art and aesthetics on another hand. <i>Advertising</i> is one of the forms of mass communication. <i>Advertising</i> is a part of business.

Author: J. Vveinhardt, 2005

emphasize advertising as a means of sponsorship or a process of the transfer of information and a communicative process. However, there are some original definitions of advertising. For instance, Jokubauskas (2003) defines advertising as a type of the fine arts or social activity, and presents advertising as the liveliest element of business. Johnson (at Kotler, 2003) emphasizes, that advertising is a big promise, and R. Šimašius (2004) understands advertising as the right to choose. Other authors present secondary definitions of advertising, which include image formation

(Mažeikaitė, 2001a), strange phenomenon (Miliūnaitė, 2004), the branch close to perfection (Johnson, 1970 at Įaņša, 2001). However, they all do not emphasize advertising as the communication process directly, and do not identify advertising and the transfer of information directly. And that is the most important focus of advertising.

Most authors, presented in the table, define the concept of *advertising* as the main means of transfer of information about a commodity or a service to a consumer on purpose to attract consumer's attention, control it and keep it

for as long as possible. Therefore, advertising is often identified with popularization and promotion.

In summary we can state that advertising is a means of communication, popularizing a commodity or service and influencing the consumer's decision about the purchase of a certain commodity or service.

3. The main functions of advertising as the means of information transfer

Yet before Lithuania had joined the European Union (hereafter – EU), A. Pabedinskaitė (2004) stated, that Lithuanian companies would feel the possibility of change, and with joining the EU the participation in international markets, which stimulates to pay more attention to the area of advertising, would become more active (Pabedinskaitė, 2004).

People cannot cover broadening and deepening streams of information any more, so a larger part of information remains unnoticed and unmemorised by people. To get the address to be at least noticed, you need quite a lot of intensive efforts (Mažeikaitė, 2001b).

Information reaches consumers if the following four conditions are assured (Kinduryš, 2002):

- when a service offered by a company is valuable or useful to a consumer;
- the consumer wants to get the service in a certain moment;
- the consumer perceives that he/she is able to pay for the desired service;
- the consumer sees or hears information about the wanted service.

J. Stankevičienė (2002) proposes that only the companies, which satisfy the consumers' needs innovatively and comprehensively, i.e. offer not only a product itself, but also solve the consumers' problems, will be able to remain in the market under the conditions of sharp competition. Advertising messages differ from usual information messages, as they fulfil the function of persuasion of a person and have a particular aim – to encourage purchasing of one or other goods or services (Ильванов, 2003). In A. Baverstock's (2002) opinion, the most effective tactics of

marketing has to be distinguished by simplicity: a suitable slogan is so definite that it is easy to memorise it at once; information letter offers a product so attractively that a reader fills in an order form straight away. However, it is necessary to note that it is not easy to reach such simplicity. For this purpose you have to know the market, for which it is intended, thoroughly. After all, the goal of advertising is not only to inform a consumer, but also to encourage him/her to perform or not to perform a certain action (Šulcas, 2004).

Although situations can often overcome disposition, social psychologists do not treat an individual as passive. It turns out that any person reacts individually in the same situation: it depends on personal qualities, traits and culture (Маїєрс, 2002).

J. Stankevičienė (2004) proposes that the choice of a consumer depends on how a product meets the needs and values of every group. If the product conflicts with cultural norms, it will be accepted worse.

Nowadays a consumer faces many services and goods, receives a lot of information about them. Every company tries to attract consumer's attention to its goods or services in different ways on purpose to sell them sooner or later. However, selling or buying (on the part of a consumer) is the result of the process of the decision, which consists of several stages (Bublytė, 2004).

Every talentedly created advertisement is good in its own way. However, even in very talentedly created advertisements there are common links. One of them is the means, which make an advertising message really effective (Kaziliūnaitė, 2005). As V. Zuzevičius states, every successfully created commercial leaves in our memory (it is of no account – in consciousness or subconsciousness) a certain clear and strong record, a seal, which is very difficult to delete by other advertisements and even by personal experience (Zuzevičius, 2004). The aims of advertising are realised when implementing the functions of advertising, which, according to Čereška (2004), are subdivided into *economic* and *social* functions (which should be defined as spheres of advertising, not as functions themselves) on macro level. The functions of advertising are concerned

Source: framed by authors, 2006

Fig 1. Spheres of the functions of advertising

with its communication goals – to remind, to persuade, to inform. These goals of advertising are the starting point, when the functions of advertising are defined. Čereška (2004), distinguishing the macro level of the functions of advertising, does not emphasize the functions of advertising in *psychological* and *cultural* spheres at all. Therefore it is advisable to state that the functions of advertising on macro level involve not only social, economic, but psychological and cultural spheres as well (see Fig 1).

Creation of good advertisements and placing them where the potential consumers will see them requires a proper knowledge of the market. Therefore the spheres presented in Fig 1 are important for the analysis of the functions of advertising, which are explained in Table 2.

The technology of demand formation and sales promotion, used by travelling merchants, has been in use from the Middle Ages till the end of the 19th century. The Americans used the abbreviation SLB (*stay, look, buy*) for this technology. In the first decade of the 20th century W. Scott (1903, 1908), one of the first authors, who wrote about the psychology of advertising, started to improve this technology. And an American marketologist E.K. Strong (1925) finally formed a formula-concept AIDA, which existed till 1975. Later this formula-concept was improved and became DIPADA. In the formula-concept AIDA the following **functions of advertising** are presented:

A – (*Attention*) to attract attention, using proper headings and openings, so that a consumer would be ready to listen to an advertising message.

I – (*interest*) to interest a consumer by presenting necessary basic/additional information in order to familiarize the consumer with the advantages of a product or service.

D – (*Desire*) to keep the need, stating the reasons, why it is worth to buy.

A – (*Action*) to act, i.e. to make a buy/sell transaction.

Another formula of **the functions of advertising** is DIPADA, which means:

D – (*Definition*) to define consumer’s needs and wants.

I – (*identification*) to identify products/services with consumer’s needs.

P – (*Proof*) to prove that advertised products/services meet consumer’s needs.

A – (*Acceptance*) to gain consumer’s acceptance that the advertised products/services meet consumer’s needs.

D – (*Desire*) to keep the consumer’s need to purchase/buy the product or service.

A – (*Action*) to act, i.e. to make a buy/sell transaction.

The process and development of these formulas-concepts determined the alteration of the conception of the market. In the second half of the 20th century the sellers’ market became the buyers’ market on international scale.

Analysing **functions of advertising**, we can present the different **attitude towards the influence of advertising on consumers** than the attitude of W. Scott and E. K. Strong. R. Dominick (1993) presents another partition of the functions of advertising. With reference to R. Dominick (1993), the main functions of advertising are the following:

- a) *Marketing*. Helps companies sell goods.
- b) *Educational*. People find out about new products and services, learn to use them, go deep into the essence of the advertised products or services.
- c) *Economic*. This is an opportunity for new businessmen to get into the market. Competition improves production and influences the pricing policy.
- d) *Social*. Advertising stimulates production and raises the standard of living.
- e) *Informational*. This function assures that consumers will receive all information about manufacturers of goods, possibilities of the usage of goods.

Table 2. Explanations of spheres of the functions of advertising

SPHERES OF FUNCTIONS OF ADVERTISING	EXPLANATION
Economic	Helps balance supply and demand of goods and services in the market. Helps consumers to view the market better and orient there easier. Forms the needs, stimulates the rise of new ones or modify the old ones. Influences production actively and helps improve it. Helps rationalize the circulation of goods. Forms public opinion about the culture of service in trade and services, etc.
Social	Broadens consumers' outlook, enriches their knowledge. Develops consumers' aesthetical taste. Popularizes healthy living, the culture of life. Teaches to protect environment, fight with inappropriate manifestation of consuming in society, etc.
Psychological	Forms the consumers' attitude towards a chosen product. Changes the consumers' attitude towards a chosen product. Influences consumers' attitude towards a chosen product.
Cultural	Emphasizes and meets the needs of a society of a certain culture. Presents the criteria, understandable, acceptable and typical to a certain culture. Conveys the norms, beliefs and traditions of a certain culture.

Note: framed by authors according to Jokubauskas, 2003; Čereška, 2004; Stankevičienė, 2005.

- f) *Communicational*. This function assures advertising-consumer communication.
- g) *Control and Correction*. These functions manifest themselves in the process of the research of advertising activity, when the opinions of consumers are surveyed (questionnaires, surveys, etc.).
- h) *Demand management*. Due to advertising a certain category of consumers is influenced.

It is obvious, that all the functions of advertising, distinguished by different authors, may be grouped into the spheres, mentioned above: economic, social, psychological, cultural.

Thus, in *economic aspect* advertising balances supply and demand, helps consumers orient in plenty of various goods, influences consumers' needs, improves production, researches the market and forms it, rationalizes selling of goods, etc. In *social aspect* advertising emphasizes new, progressive creed, develops aesthetical taste (Gečienė, 2004). In *psychological aspect* advertising forms and changes the consumers' attitude towards a chosen product, and in *cultural aspect* it emphasizes the norms, culture, traditions and beliefs, accredited in society.

4. The influence of advertising as a means of transfer of information on consumers

In everyday life most people get into the sphere of advertising activity as members of the audience of advertising. For a marketing specialist it is important to look at advertising from another side, i.e. view it as a means, which helps implement the aims of a company in marketing. In the process of implementation of goals it is important to understand and be able to assess the effectiveness of advertising (Stankevičienė, 2005). Advertising consumer is a

person, to whom the advertisement is intended, or who it may reach. Advertising consumer, i.e. its reader, buyer, a potential user of an advertised commodity or service, is an active participant of advertising market, sometimes even the initiator of advertisement. He/she often asks the disseminator of advertising or an advertising agency for the information, which he/she is interested in directly or indirectly, on his/her own initiative or through the mediation (Čereška, 2004). The assessment of the effectiveness of advertising influence is especially important to the company, organising advertising, as advertising is the investment in company's future (Jokubauskas, 2003). The effectiveness of advertising is often assessed according to the impact the advertising has on consumer. However, rather little stress is put on the aspects of the impact of advertising on consumer. Therefore, it is purposeful firstly to distinguish the aspects of the impact of advertising on consumer (see Fig 2), which may compose the formula of the impact of advertising on consumer CAFE'A (see Fig 2).

Further, the aspects of the impact of advertising on consumers are described.

1. Cognition (C). It is connected with the following elements: senses and recollections (memory, perception, thinking, speech, attention). Senses commonly arise from subconsciousness, perception comes knowingly, attention (as the most important feature of perception) is attracted by oneness, memory is the process of memorising, storage and revival, thinking generalises the reflexion of things and phenomena in consumer's consciousness.

2. Action (A). When a person noticed and read an advertisement, its impact can still be appreciable. Advertising and its means inevitably cause a certain reaction (purposeful, secondary, reverse).

Author: I. Janulienė, 2006

Fig 2. The Impact of Advertising on Consumers

3. Finances (F). This aspect is connected with consumers' spending, which may be influenced by advertising.

4. Emotions (E). Emotional component of the influence of advertising is definable by emotional relations with an advertised object, i.e. how a person estimates the advertised item – whether he feels sympathy or antipathy, he is neutral or malicious about it. Thus, these emotional reactions, caused in people by advertising, eventually form a wish or disinclination for buying an advertised object (Jokubauskas, 2003).

5. Advantage (A). It includes the ratios of consumers' financial spending, emotions and advantage of purchased things. It is necessary to note that the influence of advertising on consumers' action (e.g. to buy a product) and the cognition of the product do not have to exceed received advantage, when the product is purchased.

In this case, unlike in advertising functions, presented by SLB, AIDA and DIPADA formulas, it is purposeful to use the formula of other parameters-aspects – *CAFE'A*, which stands for *cognition, action, finances, emotions, advantage*, in order to define **the impact of advertising on consumer**. The main stress in this formula is that all the aspects of the impact of advertising on consumer (cognition, action, finances and emotions) have to match the advantage received by a consumer, who purchased a product or service.

According to D. Jokubauskas (2003), advertising influences a consumer, never mind if he/she wants it or not, because good advertising penetrates into the person's conscious and makes him/her buy an advertised item sooner or later. Every member of a modern society permanently faces advertising and can say what it is intuitively. However, it is not so easy to define the essence of the creative and dynamic area precisely. If one chooses appropriate advertising, sales increase, different difficulties (like the change of consumers' purchasing power, behaviour of competitors, vague border between one and another advertising campaign) are avoided.

Thus, the consumer is a momentum of advertising. He is a kind of creator of feedback, who decides to watch or not to watch commercials, to buy or not to buy, to go to the polls or not to go (Čereška, 2004).

5. Conclusions

1. Advertising as a means of the transfer of information, which helps realise most of the activities of a company and influence consumers purposefully. Most theorists define the concept of *advertising* as the main means of transfer of information about a commodity or a service, the aim of which is to attract consumer's attention, control it and keep it for as long as possible. Therefore advertising is often identified with popularization and promotion of an advertised commodity. Other authors identify the concept of advertising with image formation, strange phenomena, and

a branch close to perfection. However, they do not emphasize the most important focus of advertising – communication process and information transfer.

2. Different functions of advertising and their variants are pointed out in scientific literature. Some authors distinguish only social and economic functions of advertising, which should equal the spheres of the functions of advertising. Others resolve functions of advertising into marketing, demand management, informational, communicational, educational, control and correction, etc. But all these functions may be grouped into four spheres – economic, social, psychological and cultural.

3. The influence of advertising as a means of transfer of information on consumer might be assessed in the aspects of cognition, action, finances, emotion and advantage, which become a formula of the impact of advertising on consumer – *CAFE'A*. Firstly a consumer finds an advertisement, familiarizes with an advertised product. Consumer's action determines the decision to buy the advertised product or not, however, financial expenses have to match consumer's emotions and received advantage.

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